

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of 3-Aryloxy-2-benzyl-naphthoxazaphosphorine-3-oxides and 2-(4-Methylphenyl)naphthoxazaphosphorine-3-sulphides

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In continuation of our studies¹ on the synthesis of new biologically active organophosphorus heterocyclic compound, we undertook the preparation of naphthoxazaphosphorine 3-oxides/sulphides. The title compounds (1a-g) were prepared by the condensation of phosphorodichloridates with 1-benzylaminomethylnaphthol-2 in dry tetrahydrofuran in the presence of triethylamine (Scheme 1). On the other hand, the naphthoxazaphosphorine-3-sulphides (2a-e) were synthesised in two steps, through the intermediate monochloride. Synthesis of 3-chloro-2-(4-methylphenyl)naphthoxazaphosphorine-3-sulphide (1) was accomplished by the treatment of thiophosphorylchloride with 1-(4-methylanilino)methylnaphthol in the presence of triethylamine. The monochloride (1) was treated

in situ with 8-hydroxyquinolines and amines to get 2a-e (Scheme 2). The nmr spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer PE 781 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker 500 MHz instrument using TMS as internal standard. The elemental analysis was performed at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

The 1-benzylaminomethylnaphthol-2, 1-*p*-toluidinomethylnaphthol-2 and phenylphosphorodichloridates were prepared by known procedures³.

NOTES

1a-g

- 1a; R=2-Cl-C₆H₄O e; R=2-CH₃-C₆H₄O
 b; R=2,6-(CH₃)₂-C₆H₃O f; R=3-CH₃-C₆H₄O
 c; R=4-Cl-3-CH₃-C₆H₃O g; R=(Cl-CH₂CH₂)₂N
 d; R=2,4-Cl₂-C₆H₃O

Scheme 1

- 2a; R=8-Hydroxyquinolino d; R=Piperazinyl
 b; R=5-Chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline
 c; R=5,7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinolino e; R=Dibutylamino

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS 1a-g AND 2a-e*

Compd. no.	Methyl-H	Methylene-H	Aryl-H
1a	—	4.8 (2H, s) 3.5–4.3 (2H, m)	7.0–7.8 (15H, m)
b	—	—	—
c	2.2 (3H, s)	4.7 (2H, s) 3.7–4.2 (2H, m)	7.0–7.9 (14H, m)
d	2.2 (3H, s)	4.8 (2H, s) 3.6–4.2 (2H, m)	7.0–7.7 (15H, m)
e	2.4 (3H, s)	4.9 (2H, s) 3.7–4.3 (2H, m)	7.1–8.1 (15H, m)
f	2.2 (6H, s)	5.0 (2H, s) 3.7–4.3 (2H, m)	7.0–8.1 (14H, m)
g	—	4.5 (2H, s) 3.7–4.2 (2H, m) 3.2 (4H, t) 4.3 (4H, t)	7.1–7.7 (11H, m)
2a	2.3 (3H, s)	4.5–5.2 (2H, m)	6.5–8.2, 8.7–8.9 (16H, m)
b	2.3 (3H, s)	4.5–5.3 (2H, m)	6.5–8.1, 8.5–9.1 (15H, m)
c	2.3 (3H, s)	4.5–5.2 (2H, m)	6.5–8.0, 8.5–8.9 (14H, m)
d	2.4 (3H, s)	4.8–5.4 (2H, m) 2.6–3.3 (8H, m)	7.0–7.8 (10H, m)
e	2.3 (3H, s)	4.5–5.4 (2H, m) 0.7–0.8 (6H, t) 1.0–1.5 (8H, m) 3.0–3.2 (4H, m)	7.2–7.9 (10H, m)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

3-(2-Chlorophenoxy)-2,3-dihydro-2-benzyl-1H-naphth[1,2-e](1,3,2)oxazaphosphorine-3-oxide (1a): 2-Chlorophenylphosphorodichloridate (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added to a stirred mixture of 1-benzylaminomethylnaphthol-2 (2.3 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (2.02 g, 0.02 mol) in benzene (40 ml) and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and for another 2 h at 50–60°. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Triethylaminehydrochloride was separated by filtration and the solvent was removed by rotavapor. The residue obtained was washed with water and recrystallised from 2-propanol to afford 1a (3.0 g, 68%), m.p. 135–36°. Yields of the compounds were 65–69% having m.ps. 98–142°; $\nu_{\max}^2$ 1305–1300 (P=O), 1250–1200, 960–925 (P–O–C aryl) and 1070–1040, 740–700 cm⁻¹ (P–N–C aliph).

3-(8-Hydroxyquinolino)-2,3-dihydro-2-(methylphenyl)-1H-naphth[1,2-g](1,3,2)oxazaphosphorine-3-sulphide (2a): Thiophosphoryl chloride (1.7 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added to a cooled (5–10°) and stirred mixture of 1-p-toluidinomethylnaphthol-2 (2.63 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (3.03 g, 0.03 mol) in benzene (40 ml) and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and then at 40–60° for 2 h. 9-Hydroxyquinoline (1.46 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (15 ml) was then added to the reaction mix-

ture at 10–15° while stirring. It was slowly brought to room temperature and stirred for an additional 2 h. Solid triethylaminehydrochloride was separated by filtration and the solvent from the filtrate was evaporated. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from 2-propanol to get 2a as pale yellow solid (3.2 g, 64%), m.p. 161–62°. Yields of the compounds were 53–67% having m.ps. 115–162°; $\nu_{\max}^2$ 785–780 (P=S), 1 220–1 210 (P–O–C aryl), 1 065–1 050, 750–700 cm^{-1} (P–N–C aryl).

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